

Research article

Two species of butterflies new for the Western Stara Planina Mts – *Euphydryas aurinia* and *Heteropterus morpheus* and new data for another rare species

Mario Langourov¹, Stanislav Abadjiev²

(1) [Corresponding author] National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, langourov@nmnhs.com

(2) National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, abadjiev@nmnhs.com

Abstract: In the present article, we reported two new species for the Western Stara Planina Mountains – *Euphydryas aurinia* (Rottemburg, 1775), *Heteropterus morpheus* (Pallas, 1771). A confirmation of a recently discovered population of *Apatura metis* Freyer, 1829 is given too.

Keywords: distribution, *Euphydryas aurinia*, *Heteropterus morpheus*, Natura 2000, new record, Western Stara Planina Mts

Introduction

The first records of the butterfly fauna of Western Stara Planina Mountains dates back to the end of nineteenth century and beginning of twentieth century. During the last few decades, a multitude of faunistic papers covering southwestern part of the mountain were published, followed by a special book on the butterflies of the Serbian part of the mountain (Popović & Đurić, 2014) and a review article with some new data (Langourov, 2019). The last addition is a new locality of *Lycaena helle* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) (Langourov & Raeburn, 2022). With ongoing research, we discovered another two species that represent an interest as priority species of protection and expanding their known range.

New records for *Euphydryas aurinia* (Rottemburg, 1775) are filling a gap in the known distribution of the species in the Western Stara Planina Mountains. Most probably because the species has a relatively short flying period it is under-recorded in the Balkan Peninsula. Apparently, the species is more widespread in the region than previously thought and will be recorded in additional localities during future surveys.

The species inhabits grassy hillsides, woodland clearings and glades, dry shrubs, mountain meadows; damp meadows and woodland clearings (Tshikolovets, 2011).

The marsh fritillary (*Euphydryas aurinia*) is a threatened butterfly of high conservation importance in Europe, included in Annexes II and IV of the Council Directive 92/43/EEC (Council of the European Communities, 1992) and listed as Endangered (EN) in Europe (Van Swaay et al. 2010). Outside the Balkan Peninsula it has a disjunctive distribution from Eastern Pyrenees, Central and Northern Europe across Siberia and Dzhungarsky Alatau Mountains to the southern parts of the Far East, Northern Mongolia and Northern China (Tuzov et al., 2000; Tshikolovets, 2011; Tshikolovets et al., 2009, 2016).

The species *Heteropterus morpheus* (Pallas, 1771) inhabits damp meadows and woodland clearings with swamps or damp places (Tshikolovets, 2011). The new record significantly expands the known area of the species in Serbia and on the Balkan Peninsula as a whole. Its discovery shows that in the future research the species could be found in another suitable places along the Danube and/or its tributaries

Fig. 1. Map of localities of *E. aurinia*.

Fig. 2. Habitat of *E. aurinia* – Bulgaria, Montana, Martinovo, Deyanitsa Place, 43.3385713°N, 22.8288684°E – 43.3390964°N, 22.8281317°E, 1550 m.

Fig. 3. Habitat of *E. aurinia* – Bulgaria, Montana, Martinovo, Martinovo, near Vrazha Glava Peak, 43.3450984°N, 22.8062041°E, 1650 m.

Fig. 4. Habitat of *E. aurinia* – Serbia, Zaječar: Ravno Bučje, Kozarnica, Strma Reka Valley, 43.3933444°N, 22.6093095°E – 43.39553°N, 22.6063236°E, 1050 m.

Fig. 5. *E. aurinia*, Serbia, Zaječar: Ravno Bučje, 43.39481°N, 22.6071479°E, 15.vi.2022.

Fig. 6. *E. aurinia*, in copula, Serbia, Zaječar, Čuštica, 43.3612597°N, 22.5797711°E, 17.vi.2024.

Fig. 7. Habitat of *E. aurinia* – Serbia, Jabučko Ravnište Place, Babin Zub region.

in Northern Bulgaria and confirmed the historical records near Svishtov and Lovech.

Apatura metis Freyer, 1829 is strictly protected species in Serbia (Anonymous, 2016).

Material and methods

During our survey, coordinates and altitudes were obtained in the field with GPS (Garmin nüvi 2597 LMT) and through the app SmartBirds Pro.

Photographs were taken with a Panasonic DC-FZ82 camera. Butterflies are listed following the nomenclature of Tshikolovets (2011).

Results and discussion

Euphydryas aurinia

Data (Fig. 1): Bulgaria, Montana: Chiprovtsi – (A1) 43.3473436°N, 22.851563°E, 13.vi.2024, 1 specimen

Fig. 8. Map of localities of *H. morpheus*.

• Martinovo – (A2) (Fig. 2) 43.3385713°N, 22.8288684°E, 13.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (A3) (Fig. 2) 43.3390964°N, 22.8281317°E, 13.vi.2024, 1 male, 1 female (in copula); (A4) (Fig. 3) 43.3450984°N, 22.8062041°E, 13.vi.2024, 1 specimen ♦ Serbia, Zaječar: Ravno Bučje, Dojčino Vrelo – (A5) 43.3687917°N, 22.6004438°E, 16.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (A6) 43.3690033°N, 22.6008366°E, 16.vi.2024, 1 specimen; Kozarnica – (A7) (Fig. 4) 43.3933444°N, 22.6093095°E, 16.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (A8) (Fig. 4) 43.3934209°N, 22.6095203°E, 16.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (A9) (Fig. 4) 43.39481°N, 22.6071479°E, 15.vi.2022, 1 specimen (Fig. 5); (A10) (Fig. 4) 43.3948984°N, 22.6070083°E, 16.vi.2024, 2 specimens; (A11) (Fig. 4) 43.3951549°N, 22.6067169°E, 15.vi.2022, 1 specimen; (A12) (Fig. 4) 43.39553°N, 22.6063236°E, 16.vi.2024, 1 specimen; Crni Vrh – (A13) 43.4090967°N, 22.574179°E, 16.vi.2022, 1 specimen • Stanjinac, Bigar – (A14) 43.3539808°N, 22.4429918°E, 16.vi.2022, 1 specimen • Jabučko Ravnište – (A15) 43.3605453°N, 22.5798951°E, 17.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (A16) 43.3612597°N, 22.5797711°E, 17.vi.2024, 1 male, 1 female (in copula) (Fig. 6) [all records M. Langourov].

During field surveys in June 2022 and June 2024 some specimens were observed and photographed by the first author above Chiprovtsi, Bigar Waterfall, above Crni Vrh Village and at Jabučko Ravnište Place, Babin Zub region (Fig. 7). All the localities are mountain wet meadows with many flowering plants and are situated between 470 m to 1650 m. Here the species flies together with wide variety of species because of the altitude of the different localities.

Heteropterus morpheus

Data (Fig. 8): Serbia, Zaječar: Stanjinac, Bigar – (B1) (Fig. 9) 43.3534043°N, 22.4414936°E, 17.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (B2) (Fig. 9) 43.3545601°N, 22.4439013°E, 18.vi.2024, 1 specimen (Fig. 10); (B3) (Fig. 9) 43.3547078°N, 22.4438448°E, 28.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (B4) (Fig. 9) 43.35486°N, 22.4434801°E, 17.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (B5) (Fig. 9) 43.3549061°N, 22.4434036°E, 17.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (B6) (Fig. 9) 43.3549663°N, 22.4434817°E, 17.vi.2024, 1 specimen; (B7) (Fig. 9) 43.3551566°N, 22.4431133°E, 18.vi.2024, 1 specimen [all records M. Langourov].

Fig. 9. Habitat of *H. morpheus* – Serbia, Zaječar, Stanjinac, Bigar Waterfall 43.3534043°N, 22.4414936°E – 43.3551566°N, 22.4431133°E, 450 m.

Fig. 10. *H. morpheus*, Serbia, Zaječar: Stanjinac, 43.3545601°N, 22.4439013°E, 18.vi.2024.

During a field survey in June 2024 between the midday till late afternoon many mudpuddling or flying around specimens were observed and photographed by the first author at Bigar Waterfall. The locality is a riverbank with wet meadows around and it has coordinates 43.35507°N, 22.44332°E and an altitude of 460 m.

Apatura metis Freyer, 1829

During a field survey on 18.vi.2024 in the midday one mudpuddling male specimen was observed and photographed by the first author at Bigar Waterfall. The locality is a riverbank with wet meadows around and it has coordinates 43.35507°N, 22.44332°E and an altitude of 460 m. This record confirmed previous one exactly from the same place (Langourov, 2019).

Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor. As members of the editorial board, Mario Langourov and Stanislav Abadjiev withdrew from discussions and decisions on the manuscript.

References

Council of the European Communities 1992 Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the

- conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (The Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC). Official Journal of the European Communities 35: 7–50.
- Anonymous 2016 Rulebook on declaration and protection of strictly protected and protected wild species of plants, animals and fungi. Official Gazette of RS No. 5/2010, 47/2011, 32/2016 and 98/2016. (In Serbian)
- Langourov M. 2019 New data on the butterflies of Western Stara Planina Mts (Bulgaria & Serbia) (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). *Ecologica Montenegrina* 20: 119–162.
- Langourov M., Raeburn H. 2022 A new locality of the violet copper *Lycaena helle* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) on the Balkan Peninsula. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 44 (6): 41–44. <https://doi.org/10.48027/hnb.44.061>
- Popović M., Đurić M. 2014 Butterflies of Stara Planina (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea). Public enterprise “Srbijašume”, Belgrade, 208 pp.
- Tshikolovets V.V. 2011 Butterflies of Europe & the Mediterranean area. Tshikolovets Publications, 544 pp.
- Tshikolovets V.V., Kosterin O., Gorbunov P., Yakovlev R. 2016 The Butterflies of Kazakhstan. Tshikolovets Publications, 448 pp.
- Tshikolovets V.V., Yakovlev R., Balint Z. 2009 The Butterflies of Mongolia. Tshikolovets Publications, 320 pp.
- Tuzov V.K., Bogdanov P.V., Churkin S.V., Dantchenko A.V., Devyatkin A.L., Murzin V.S., Samodurov G.D., Zhdanko A.B. 2000 Guide to the Butterflies of Russia and Adjacent Territories (Lepidoptera, Rhopalocera). Vol. 2. Pensoft Publishers, Sofia–Moscow, 399 pp.
- Van Swaay C., Cuttelod A., Collins S., Maes D., López Munguira M., Šašić M., Settele J., Verovnik R., Verstrael T., Warren M., Wiemers M., Wynhof I. 2010 European Red List of Butterflies. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, x + 46 pp.
-